

Synthesis of some New 2-Methyl-3-(2-methoxy-4-arylthiocarbamidophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones as Possible Anticonvulsants

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In view of their expected M.A.O. inhibitory, C.N.S. depressant and anticonvulsant properties, twenty-one new 2-methyl-3-(2-methoxy-4-arylthiocarbamidophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones were synthesised. Some of these compounds inhibited rat brain monoamine oxidase (*in vitro*) at a concentration 1×10^{-8} mol dm⁻³ and produced protection against pentylenetetrazole-induced convulsions in mice.

A number of workers have reported that some derivatives of 4-quinazolone exhibit C.N.S.¹, hypnotic², anticonvulsant^{3,4} and analgesic⁵ activity. 2-Methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4-quinazolone was shown to be a potent anticonvulsant and superior to phenobarbitone, when used against pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures⁶. Furthermore, some carbamide⁷ and thiocarbamido^{8,9} derivatives have been found to possess pronounced anticonvulsant activity. Stimulated by these observations, we synthesised the title compounds (Scheme 1) with the hope that these might display a high order of anticonvulsant activity.

2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline was heated with various substituted-anthranils in an oil-bath to afford 2-methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-4'-nitrophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones. The latter were reduced by Raney Ni and hydrazine hydrate to their corresponding amino derivatives which were refluxed with different isothiocyanates in anhydrous benzene to furnish the title quinazolones.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

3,5-Dibromo¹⁰ and 5-iodo¹¹ anthranilic acids (1) and acetanthranils¹² (2) were prepared by the methods available in literature.

2-Methyl-3-(2-methoxy-4-nitrophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones (3): Equimolar amount of an appropriately substituted-anthranil and 2-methoxy-4-nitroaniline were heated at 150-60° in an oil-bath for 0.5 h. The solid obtained on cooling was triturated with ethanol and filtered. The crude solid was recrystallised from ethyl acetate. The compounds thus prepared were characterised by

Scheme 1

their sharp m.p., elemental analysis and by the ir spectral bands at 1660 (N=C=O), 1340 and 1520 cm⁻¹ (NO₂): **3a** (X=X'=H) (65%), m.p. 225° (Found: C, 61.38; H, 3.84; N, 13.81. C₁₆H₁₃N₃O₄ requires C, 61.73; H, 4.18; N, 13.50%); **3b** (X=X'=Br) (60%), m.p. 216-218° (Found: C, 41.59; H, 2.01; N, 8.43. C₁₆H₁₁N₃O₄Br₂ requires C, 40.93; H, 2.34; N, 8.76%); **3c** (X=I, X'=H)

TABLE 1—2-METHYL-3-(2-METHOXY-4-ARYLTHIOCARBAMIDOPHENYL)-6,8-SUBSTITUTED-4-QUINAZOLONES (5)

Sl. no.	X	X'	Ar	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
1.	H	H	Phenyl	170	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	66.76 (66.34)	4.57 (4.80)	13.18 (13.46)
2.*	H	H	4-Tolyl	196	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	66.54 (66.97)	5.34 (5.11)	13.26 (13.02)
3.	H	H	4-Chlorophenyl	210	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SCI	60.88 (61.26)	8.95 (4.21)	12.12 (12.48)
4.*	Br	Br	4-Methoxyphenyl	101	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂	48.13 (47.60)	3.53 (3.31)	8.94 (9.27)
5.	Br	Br	4-Chlorophenyl	198	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂ Cl	45.69 (45.35)	2.56 (2.79)	8.87 (9.20)
6.	Br	Br	4-Bromophenyl	157	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂	42.68 (42.26)	2.82 (2.60)	8.25 (8.57)
7.	I	H	Phenyl	140	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SI	50.48 (50.92)	3.72 (3.60)	10.54 (10.83)
8.	I	H	4-Tolyl	150	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ SI	51.37 (51.79)	3.94 (3.77)	9.73 (10.07)
9.	I	H	4-Chlorophenyl	180	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SICI	47.51 (47.87)	3.42 (3.12)	9.36 (9.71)
10.	H	H	4-Ethoxyphenyl	199	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	64.89 (65.21)	5.47 (5.21)	11.78 (12.17)
11.	H	H	4-Methoxyphenyl	211	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	64.13 (64.57)	5.26 (4.93)	12.23 (12.55)
12.	H	H	4-Bromophenyl	174	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SBr	66.21 (65.75)	8.54 (8.83)	11.98 (11.31)
13.*	Br	Br	Phenyl	185	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂	48.49 (48.03)	3.45 (3.13)	9.43 (9.75)
14.	Br	Br	3-Chlorophenyl	155	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂ Cl	45.76 (45.35)	3.13 (2.79)	8.86 (9.20)
15.	Br	Br	4-Tolyl	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂	48.61 (48.97)	3.12 (3.40)	9.27 (9.52)
16.	I	H	4-Ethoxyphenyl	185	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ SI	51.64 (51.19)	3.43 (3.92)	9.28 (9.55)
17.	I	H	3-Chlorophenyl	177	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SICI	47.54 (47.87)	3.43 (3.12)	9.47 (9.71)
18.*	I	H	4-Methoxyphenyl	121	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ SI	49.93 (50.34)	3.29 (3.67)	9.43 (9.79)
19.	H	H	3-Chlorophenyl	190	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SCI	60.73 (61.26)	4.46 (4.21)	12.15 (12.43)
20.	Br	Br	4-Ethoxyphenyl	105	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂	48.93 (48.54)	3.87 (3.55)	9.34 (9.06)
21.	I	H	4-Bromophenyl	143	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ SIBr	44.87 (44.44)	3.17 (2.89)	8.76 (9.01)

* $\nu_{\max}$ 1120-1160 (C=S str.), 1600 (Ar), 1660 (N-C=O str.), 2990 (OH str.) and 3200-3300 cm^{-1} (NH str.).

(64%), m.p. 195° (Found: C, 43.46; H, 2.96; N, 9.32. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₄I requires C, 43.93; H, 2.74; N, 9.61%).

2-Methyl-3-(2-methoxy-4-aminophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones (4): **3** (0.004 M) was dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) and Raney Ni (0.5 g) was added to it. Hydrazine hydrate (99%) was then carefully added at room temperature and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 4-6 h. The resulting solution was filtered and ethanol was distilled off from the filtrate. The residue was recrystallised from ethyl acetate. The compounds were characterised by their m.p., elemental analysis and disappearance of ir bands for NO₂ (1340 and 1520 cm^{-1}) and appearance of bands for NH₂ (3300-3400 cm^{-1}): **4a** (X=X'=H) (60%), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 68.04; H, 4.98; N, 14.69. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₄ requires C, 68.32; H, 5.33; N, 14.95%); **4b** (X=X'=Br) (56%), m.p. 178° (Found: C, 43.38; H, 2.61; N, 9.24. C₁₆H₁₂N₂O₄Br₂ requires C,

43.73; H, 2.96; N, 9.56%); **4c** (X=I, X'=H) (58%), m.p. 166° (Found: C, 47.64; H, 3.21; N, 10.53. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₄I requires C, 47.17; H, 3.43; N, 10.32%).

2-Methyl-3-(2-methoxy-4-arylthiocarbamidophenyl)-6,8-substituted-4-quinazolones (5): A mixture of **4** (0.002 M) and an arylisothiocyanate (0.002 M) in anhydrous benzene (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6-8 h. Excess benzene was distilled off and the solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds so prepared were characterised by their m.p., elemental analysis and ir spectral bands (Table 1).

Pharmacology:

Six compounds were subjected to monoamine oxidase and anticonvulsant activities.

ALD₅₀ and gross behavioural effects: ALD₅₀ was determined following the method of Horn¹² and the gross behaviour studies were carried out

following Turner¹⁴. Different doses of compounds including 1/5th of the ALD₅₀ were administered i.p. in groups of animals, and then observed for 6 h and 24 h for the sign of stimulation or depression. Only compound 18 was found to be depressant and the rest showed no effect.

Monoamine oxidase activity : The spectrophotometric method was used for the determination of MAO activity of rat brain homogenate using benzylamine as substrate¹⁵.

Anticonvulsant activity : Anticonvulsant activity¹⁶ of the compounds was determined against pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures in mice of either sex weighing 16-20 g. Group of 5 albino mice pretreated with 1/5th ALD₅₀ dose of compounds i.p., were injected pentylenetetrazole (80 mg/kg) subcutaneously after 1 h. The number of animals not exhibiting convulsions during 60 min after injection of pentylenetetrazole were expressed in terms of percentage protection.

Results and Discussion

The inhibitory effects of six of the synthesised substituted-4-quinazolones on MAO activity of rat brain homogenate have been recorded in Table 2. These produced 25.6 to 52.8% inhibition of rat brain

monoamineoxidase at a final concentration of 1×10^{-8} mol dm³. Substitution of halogen at positions 6 and 8 of quinazolone nucleus resulted in decreased MAO inhibitory activity. Only compound 11, however, showed 20% protection against pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures in mice.

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TABLE 2

Compd. no.	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg	Gross effect	Pentylenetetrazole seizure test, % protection	M.A.O. inhibition** %
2.	>1000	None	Nil	45.8
5.	>1000	None	Nil	88.5
7.	>1000	None	Nil	26.8
11.	681	None	20	52.8
18.	>1000	Depressant	Nil	35.5
19.	1000	None	Nil	25.6

* Correspond to Sl. no. in Table 1.

** Mean values of two experiments, all compounds were used at final concentration of 1×10^{-8} mol dm³.